

2015-GE-357613

TPE - 02.10.2015 09:10:10

Esvr No: FT / 0

SEARCH REPORT

Request No: TR 2014/242	Date of Receipt: 17 April 2015 (17.04.2015)
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Application No 2013/05054	Filing date (day/month/year) 29 April 2013 (29.04.2013)	(Earliest) Priority Date (day/month/year)
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Applicant(s) ERDAL CAN ALKOCLAR et al.

Title of invention Composition for antiviral use

This search report consists of a total of 2 sheets

It is also accompanied by a copy of each prior art document cited in this report 49 sheets

- Search on the State of the Art
 Additional search on the State of the Art
- All claims were found searchable
 Certain claims were found unsearchable, see Box I
- Certain explanations to the search report, see Box II
- The application concerns:
 - pharmaceutical products/substances or their process of preparation
 - veterinary products/substances or their process of preparation

SEARCH REPORT

Application No
2013/05054

A. CLASSIFICATION OF SUBJECT MATTER *A61K 31/58 (2006.01)*
A61P 31/12 (2006.01)

According to International Patent Classification (IPC)

B. FIELDS SEARCHED

Minimum documentation searched (classification system followed by classification symbols)
A61K 31/56, 31/58, A61P 31/00, 31/12

Electronic data base consulted during the search (name of data base and, where practicable, search terms used)
PatSearch (RUPTO internal), USPTO, PAJ, Esp@cenet, Information Retrieval System of FIPS

C. DOCUMENTS CONSIDERED TO BE RELEVANT

Category*	Citation of document, with indication, where appropriate, of the relevant passages	Relevant to claim No
X A	US 2012/0252768 A1 (LION CORPORATION) 04.10.2012, abstract, [0018]-[0029], [0041], [0068], tables 1-8	1-2 3-5
A	WO 2009/094177 A1 (RAPTOR THERAPEUTICS INC. et al.) 30.07.2009	1-5
A	KOCHAN Ewa et al. The production of ginsenosides in hairy root cultures of American Ginseng, Panax quinquefolium L. and their antimicrobial activity. In Vitro Cell.Dev.Biol.-Plant (2013) 49:24-29	1-5
A	DENNIS V.S. et al. The Pharmacologically Active Constituents of White and Red Ginseng Root [online]. Retrieved from the Internet: <URL: http://www.wellgenex.com/files/The%20Pharmacologically%20Active%20Constituents%20of%20White%20and%20Red%20Ginseng%20Root.pdf >	1-5

Further documents are listed in the continuation of Box C.

See patent family annex

* Special categories of cited documents:

<p>"A" document defining the general state of the art which is not considered to be of particular relevance</p> <p>"P" document published prior to the filing date but later than the priority date claimed</p> <p>"X" document of particular relevance; the claimed invention cannot be considered novel or cannot be considered to involve an inventive step when the document is taken alone</p>	<p>"Y" document of particular relevance; the claimed invention cannot be considered to involve an inventive step when the document is combined with one or more other such documents, such combination being obvious to a person skilled in the art</p> <p>"&" document member of the same patent family</p>
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Date of mailing of the search report: 17 August 2015 (17.08.2015)

Name and mailing address of the International Searching Authority FIPS 30-1, Berezhkovskaya nab., G-59, GSP-3, Moscow, 125993, RU Facsimile No. (499) 243-33-37	Authorized officer Ivkina I. Telephone No. (499) 240-25-91
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